

Art carpet weaving is one of the forces that lifts the human mood

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Annotation

This article describes in detail the art of tapestry, one of the new types of applied art, the creation of work of tapestry and its impact on the human mood, its psychological features.

Keywords

Tapestry, moving fresco, human impact, thematic range, magical works, modern world, canvases, landscape motifs, pure, autumn paintings, still life, Italy, conclusion.

Works of folk applied art have a high value not only for their decoration, beautiful forms, antiquity, but also for their deep philosophical, educational and spiritual features.

One of the new types of applied art is tapestry art. Initially he speaks a poetic language peculiar to him. At first glance, the art of tapestry is far from the contrast of the day, but it leaves a trace of time in its essence. In many works, one can easily see the reasons for concern for the preservation of our civilization, the natural world.

What sets it apart - the "living fresco"? The decisive role here is played by the texture of the woven surface, the material that provides any monumental image

with an aura close to that of man. This aspect represents the main point of the “moving fresco” aesthetics. The original purpose of any fabric and genetically - tapestry - is to warm and decorate. Tapestries are like magical symbols that harmonize the surrounding space and the inner world of the person looking at them. These are original beautiful pictures “written” with strings, delivering a rich flow of information to the viewer.

Tapestries radiate joy, peace, reflect the charming beauty of the world around us, these people are missing in our difficult and difficult times.

Take a look at the published reproductions presented in the catalog - first the works of the authors, in fact “good” and “different”.

Tapestries fit perfectly into a modern interior. On the walls, just like the ornaments, there are beautiful paintings depicting natural landscapes, still lifes, animals and birds, their natural habitats, white snow-covered expanses, flourishing steppes, taiga and exotic forests. Fully found silhouettes, movements, postures create direct, sometimes impressive, sometimes terrifying images. Each picture is a poem about the beauty of the world, a symbolic image built on clear field observations.

Tapestries are easy to imagine at home; they relieve the boredom and boredom of standardizing townhouses, reminding us of the beauty of nature, pleasant memories and meditation, contemplation, a healthy rest in the bosom of nature.

Whatever picture you see - the beauty, the uniqueness of the shapes and images is in front of you. This is how a tone “painted” with a color code sounds like on a canvas. The joy of life is conveyed to the viewer from the canvases

Just as you can't enter the same river twice, tapestries are accepted in a new style each time. Each time the work creates a different mood. Sometimes - well: I want to ascend to heaven, and perhaps I want to find all these beauties that the master found somewhere and showed us in his works; sometimes - a little sad, but the

reason for this was that through art it was possible to convey the whole air, all its worries and sorrows, darkness and light, very finely and lightly.

The play of warm, soft, wonderful colors creates a particularly uplifting mood - creating harmony with the audience, lyrically adapting it - to an enlightened mood.

Some canvases are amazing in their integrity and perfection, while others leave room for imagination. As Max Frish, a well-known classic of European literature, points out, what we want to fill them with really fascinates us ...

The thematic range is paintings of different genres, mainly landscape, floral, decorative motifs, figures of people, animals, birds; nature is a landscape. Landscapes, still lifes, genre landscapes in life - all of these stand out for their spontaneity and sincerity.

When we look at tapestry paintings, involuntary images float before us - distant, fantastic countries, landscapes; in the bright mix of beautiful pictures we find many fantastically beautiful plants, various fairy-tale heroes, strange architectural forms ...

You look at these magical works - and you feel as if you are interacting with the landscape with your heart, immersed in the paradise around you, and relaxing with your soul.

The modern world is a stormy current in which man loses touch with nature - the most precious thing he has - the original. The artificial, "man-made" world created by human beings absorbs our consciousness and leaves a certain mark on our perception of the world. Most of the canvases are dedicated to the very theme of nature, which reminds man of where he came from and where he is a member. On canvases, nature is always alive, beautiful and uniquely changing and at the same time unique in its set beauty.

Landscape motifs remain a favorite for the viewer, where it serves as a reflection of some theatrical action that takes place around them, invisible at a glance. Not

everyone sees this movement, but nature reveals its “secret” to a grateful audience who knows how to see it.

Looking at the scenery, we feel the humidity of the air, a morning full of soft sunlight, or a warm afternoon, as well as the coolness quietly hidden under the crowns of the trees.

Some landscapes want to be called a frozen moment for contemplation time. This allows the viewer to feel and understand the depicted silence and use the magic moment to cross the line between the two realities to see the “truth in general” and the “canvas truth” and slow down the time, movement, rhythm and self-image. found in the landscape, where the artist left a piece of the heart. The spectator is captivated by simple motifs, where a concentrated wise silence is heard.

Favorite landscape objects are edges with water. These are images of quiet rivers planted with tall trees, with their fan-shaped broad branches spread out thoughtfully; or calm reservoirs with intricate plastic of steep shores; mountain streams and twisting streams that playfully descend from scenic slopes; a demonstration of the pulsating flow of spring rain. The whole world is reflected in the image of water ...

As in the mirror, the clouds are reflected in the lake, and the dome of the lake temple is probably perceived as a temple of nature

“Pure” nature landscapes, forest spaces, “portraits” of trees, seasonal conditions in quiet and deserted corners of nature predominate.

Autumn paintings are dominated by fiery orange and golden ocher tones. The element of pure emerald and silver pearl colors of spring is culminating in elegant and graceful landscapes. Winter has become a favorite theme with its sheer distances, the dazzling whiteness of the snow playing in the sun. Winter. Silence. And on the mountains - the endless blues of the cold winter sky with cold

transparent clouds floating slowly across the horizon. Peace and glorious solemnity stem from these quietly limited rhythms

Tapestries reflect the beauty of changing nature: bad weather and bright sun, the breath of the fields, the transparency of the birch forest. Among the landscapes, the clouds occupy a special place as a symbol of loyalty and blessing. Observing and depicting them in different states of nature - on an open day, in the rain, or on the eve of an approaching thunderstorm, we discover the diverse beauty of nature in its ancient power.

And how we want to live in huts lost in the foothills. And the mountains seem to be living a life independent of us. And we must come out of these little houses and attain the glory of the mountains, they do not die, but only freeze; and do not show your power over them.

The creative mood combined with nature, which undoubtedly falls into its rhythm, structure, spirit, is distinguished by still lifes, where flowers, vegetables, fruits, household items are painted in a very juicy, textured, free and inspired brush. Hugging each other or watching a certain space pause, things stand and lie on the mirror surface of the table - vases and glasses, figurines and clocks, fruits and flowers ...

Immersed in still lifes, images of flowers, the artist skillfully combined them, saturating the surrounding space with air, light and color. Bouquets are noteworthy, they demonstrate the author's ability to create compositions. The viewer feels the author's attitude towards this or that flower in relation to the unusually delicate material that carries particles of worldly intelligence and harmony.

Peonies, irises, poppies are especially inspiring ...

Italy is a unique country that has attracted the attention of several artist galaxies. The rhythm of the laconic planes is compositionally and colorfully balanced, which slows down the flow of time.

The author's sharpness and experience are reflected in the modification of the usual Italian motifs.

We emphasize another aspect of the art of tapestry - in the works appear fairy tales, awakens eternal and pleasant images and childhood memories, the world of fantasy is demonstrated. It allows you to see the world of nature and things with cheerful, vibrant, grateful eyes.

The series of children's tapestries is stunning and cozy, reminiscent of pictures for children's drawings or children's books. Thinking of them, you dive into your involuntary childhood and believe that it is in these cities and in these houses that the naughty Carlsson, the disobedient Buratino, and his father, Carlo, live. Grandpa and woman live in a secluded village hut. And the ryaba chicken in the yard is in charge ...

The portrait gallery features images of children and women that combine the deep psychology of states, the smooth expression of watercolors, a focus on limited facial expressions, and a gentle accompaniment to backgrounds.

Thus, the tapestry synthesized the features of many types of fine art. It is a manifestation of the general artistic processes taking place in culture today - the eradication of boundaries, the interpenetration and unification of different genres. Due to the richness of the problems, they are distinguished by beautiful width, graphic accuracy of the drawing and monumental forms. They retain the eternal distinctive features of the tapestry - decorative and poetic.

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